

EDUCATIONAL MODEL FOR DEVELOPING TOLERANCE: BASED ON THE NEEDS OF THE SOCIAL WORK FIELD.

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Annotation: This article discusses an educational model aimed at developing tolerance competence, which is modern and relevant for the field of social work. Tolerance is a guarantee of social stability, intercultural understanding and respect for human rights. The article reveals the content of the concept of tolerance, the needs of the field of social work, as well as the theoretical and methodological foundations of the model developed based on effective forms and technologies of teaching.

Keywords: tolerance, social work, educational model, competence, pedagogical approach, intercultural dialogue, empathy.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ijtimoiy ish sohasi uchun zamonaviy va dolzarb bo'lgan tolerantlik kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim modeli yoritiladi. Tolerantlik bu ijtimoiy barqarorlik, madaniyatlararo murosa va inson huquqlariga hurmat garovi hisoblanadi. Maqolada tolerantlik tafakkurining mazmuni, ijtimoiy ish sohasi ehtiyojlari, shuningdek, o'qitishning samarali shakllari va texnologiyalari asosida ishlab chiqilgan modelning nazariy-metodik asoslari ochib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: tolerantlik, ijtimoiy ish, ta'lim modeli, kompetensiya, pedagogik yondashuv, madaniyatlararo muloqot, empatiya.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается образовательная модель, направленная на развитие толерантной компетентности, которая является современной и актуальной для сферы социальной работы. Толерантность гарантия социальной стабильности, межкультурного взаимопонимания и уважения прав человека. В статье раскрывается содержание толерантной установки, потребности сферы социальной работы, а также теоретико-методологические основы разработанной модели на основе эффективных форм и технологий обучения.

Ключевые слова: толерантность, социальная работа, образовательная модель, компетентность, педагогический подход, межкультурная коммуникация, эмпатия.

Introduction. The coexistence of a multi-ethnic, multi-faith and culturally diverse population in modern society requires the active implementation of values such as tolerance, tolerance and intercultural understanding. These

competencies have become a professional necessity, especially for specialists working in the field of social services.

The field of social work requires an empathetic and fair approach to working with people from many social categories and solving their problems. Therefore, the formation of a tolerant mindset in students studying in the field of social work is a priority task today. The content of tolerance and the needs of the field of social work

Tolerance is a person's respectful approach to representatives of other worldviews, beliefs, nations, cultures, the ability to show empathy and compromise. This is not only a personal quality, but also a necessary competence in social activity.

Needs of the field of social work:

- Working with people with disabilities;
- Communication with the elderly, lonely people and people with disabilities;
- Working with migrants and national minorities;
- Working with victims of violence and troubled families.[1]

These activities require a high level of intercultural sensitivity and tolerance.

The need for an educational model focused on developing tolerance

Traditional education emphasizes the provision of knowledge. However, in social work education, the development of personal competencies, especially skills such as tolerance, empathy, and communication culture, is a priority. In this context, it is necessary to develop an educational model focused on developing tolerance.

The educational model focused on developing tolerance is a systematic pedagogical approach aimed at developing social and moral values in students, such as tolerance, mutual respect, and tolerance for the opinions and beliefs of others. The main goal of this model is to form social responsibility and a positive attitude towards differences in students, as well as to develop skills for effective communication with different groups in society.

The main goals of the educational model aimed at building tolerance:

- Understanding and respecting others: Teaching students to accept differences in different cultures, nationalities, religions and beliefs.
- Developing empathy and sympathy: Encouraging students to understand the situation of others and to be sincere towards their situation.

- Constructive problem solving: Teaching compromise and tolerant approaches to resolving social conflicts.[2]

Methods used in education to build tolerance:

1. Interactive educational methods:

- o Training and psychological exercises: Conducting various psychological exercises and trainings to develop empathy and gentleness towards others in students.

- o Role-playing games and dramas: Teaching students to communicate effectively with others using role-playing games and dramatic approaches aimed at understanding differences and building tolerance.

2. Case Study:

To develop students' skills in understanding the position of others and solving problems positively through the analysis of real-life examples and situations.

3. Social Projects and Assignments:

To develop students' ability to work with diverse groups, collaborate, and build mutual respect through projects and activities related to social issues.

4. Intercultural communication:

Teaching intercultural communication and encouraging them to show kindness towards each other. This method helps students to better understand other cultures and different societies.[3]

The main components of the educational model aimed at forming tolerance:

1. Cognitive component:

Theoretical knowledge about tolerance is taught: stereotypes about others, ethnic and cultural differences, social justice, human rights, etc.

Students are given the opportunity to learn about other cultures and ways of life, to understand differences.

2. Emotional component:

Developing empathy in students, understanding the situation of others, kindness and sympathy for others.

Through this component, students learn to feel mutual respect, patience and tolerance.

3. Moral component:

Moral foundations of tolerance: justice, equality, respect for human rights. To teach students to be fair and tolerant, to show respect for the common values of humanity.

4. Social component:

To develop in students the skills of working in a team and effectively managing relationships with different social groups.

5. Volitional component:

To develop in students patience, working with opposing views and a positive approach in difficult situations.[4]

Educational practice of building tolerance:

- Tolerance in the classroom: Ensuring social stability by showing respect for others in the classroom and listening to their opinions.

- Inclusive education: Providing equal opportunities for all students, as well as teaching empathy and tolerance for students with disabilities or other unique characteristics.

- Intercultural activities: Building tolerance among different nationalities, ethnic groups, or beliefs in the classroom through intercultural activities and activities.

Strategies for building tolerance in education:

1. Textbooks and teaching materials: Including teaching materials about tolerance, justice, and human rights.

2. Teacher training: Preparing teachers through special trainings and courses aimed at building tolerance.

3. Personal examples: Teaching teachers to teach tolerance and tolerance through their own examples and conversations.[5]

Benefits of a tolerance-oriented educational model:

- Social stability: Ensuring stability and peace in society by teaching students to be tolerant and tolerant of others.

- Respect and solidarity between different groups: Students learn to respect different nationalities, cultures and beliefs.

- Development of empathy and sympathy: Students feel mutual respect and kindness towards each other.

Conclusion. A tolerance-oriented educational model is a model that fully reflects the needs of the social work field, is practice-oriented and encourages personal development. Organizing the educational process on the basis of this model not only strengthens the professional training of a social work specialist, but also contributes to stability and social balance in society.

References:

1. Vaxabov A., Xajibakiev Sh. Aholini ijtimoiy himoya qilishning tarkibi va manzilliligini kuchaytirish muammolari: xalqaro tajriba va milliy xususiyatlar / "Ijtimoiy sohani modernizatsiyalash va rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari"

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya materiallari to'plami. T., 2018. B. 14.

2. The Student's Companion to Social Policy. Fourth Edition. Edited by Pete Alcock, Margaret May, and Sharon Wright. / UK 2012. John Wiley & Sons Ltd. 49 p.

3. World Social Protection Report 2014/15: Building economic recovery, inclusive development and social justice International Labour Office - Geneva: ILO, 2014. 34 p.

4. РуноваТГ. Демография: Учебное пособие. М:МГИУ,2002. 64 с

5.Абидова З.А. Понятийные аспекты феномена «толерантность». //Научный Вестник Самаркандского государственного университета. – Самарканд, 2017. –No 4 (104). –С. 165-168.